

DECICE

DEVICE-EDGE-CLOUD INTELLIGENT COLLABORATION FRAMEWORK

Grant Agreement: 101092582

D5.3 Development Environment Deployed for Phase 1 and 2

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 101092582.

Document Information

Deliverable number:	D5.3
Deliverable title:	Development Environment Deployed for Phase 1 and 2
Deliverable version:	1.0
Work Package number:	WP5
Work Package title:	Deployment, Validation and Performance Assessment
Responsible partner	E4
Due Date of delivery:	2024-05-31
Actual date of delivery:	2024-05-31
Dissemination level:	PU
Type:	DEM
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Project name:	Device-Edge-Cloud Intelligent Collaboration framEwork
Project Acronym:	DECICE
Project starting date:	2022-12-01
Project duration:	36 months
Rights:	DECICE Consortium

Document History

Version	Date	Partner	Description
0.1	2024-04-12	E4	First version of ToC
0.2	2024-04-19	E4, TOP-IX	Revised ToC
0.3	2024-05-24	E4	First stable draft
0.4	2024-05-27	MarUn, GWDG, UniBo	Round of review
1.0	2024-05-31	E4	Final version

Acknowledgement: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 10192582.

Disclaimer: The content of this publication is the sole responsibility of the authors, and in no way represents the view of the European Commission or its services.

Executive Summary

This deliverable, led by E4, provides a description of the hardware and software setup that will host the DECICE framework based on the initial specifications collected in D5.2. The document aims to showcase the work in progress related to the development and mapping of the applications comprising the use cases onto the deployment environment. Due to delays in the procurement of the DECICE physical infrastructure by E4, attributed to current pressures on the supply chains of components, an additional legacy computing cluster has been made available by E4 to mitigate the impact of this problem on the project timeline. This legacy cluster will be used temporarily to support the integration of preliminary versions of the applications and to resolve all the potential issues in the implementation.

To ensure the deliverable is self-contained, it contains a concise summary of the key elements of the framework and a brief description of the use cases. Additionally, it describes the baseline architecture used to activate a preliminary deployment of the use cases, where UC1 and UC3 have been used to debug and tune this initial solution. Lastly, it outlines the next steps to transition this baseline system into the final DECICE framework during the remainder of the Work Package 5 execution.

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1 Purpose and Scope of the Deliverable

The purpose of this deliverable is to share the initial deployment results on the development environment for which a Phase 1 (based on a single site) and a Phase 2 (2 sites) are defined, ensuring future access for all project members, with a particular emphasis in this phase on the application providers of UC1 and UC3. The content of the deliverable is based on the previous deliverables D5.1 and D5.2. The deployment was defined and implemented, considering the need to mitigate the delay in the procurement of the hardware foreseen in the final project development environment. E4 led this task in WP5 by actively collecting information and contributions from all partners involved as per the guidelines defined in section 5.

2 Publishable Summary

This deliverable, led by E4, details the setup of the hardware and software infrastructure intended to support the DECICE framework. Based on the initial specifications outlined in D5.2, this document highlights the ongoing efforts to develop and map the applications for the designated use cases onto the deployment environment.

Due to unforeseen delays in the procurement of the required physical infrastructure, primarily caused by current global supply chain constraints, an alternative solution has been implemented. E4 has provisioned a legacy computing cluster to serve temporarily. This measure ensures that the integration of preliminary application versions proceeds without further impacting the project timeline, allowing for early identification and resolution of any implementation issues.

For comprehensive understanding, the deliverable includes:

- A succinct overview of the DECICE framework's key components,
- Descriptions of the use cases with a particular focus on UC1 (Smart City Infrastructure for Autonomous Driving) and UC3 (Disaster Management and Emergency Response),
- An overview of the baseline architecture that has been employed to facilitate a preliminary deployment of these use cases.

Furthermore, the document outlines strategic steps to transition from this initial setup to the final configuration of the DECICE framework, aiming for completion within the ongoing Work Package 5. This phased approach not only addresses immediate challenges but also sets the stage for subsequent validation and scaling activities.

3 Project Objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of the following macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1.1 of the project plan:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable
(O1) Develop a solution that allows to leverage a compute continuum ranging from cloud and HPC to edge and IoT.	Availability of a heterogeneous computing cluster with CPUs, GPUs, and edge nodes.
(O2) Develop a scheduler supporting dynamic load balancing for energy-efficient compute orchestration, improved use of green energy, and automated deployment.	The heterogeneous cluster and the deployed Kubernetes-based software stack enable the exploration of scheduler optimization.
(O3) Design and implement an API that increases control over network, computing and data resources.	The system initially demonstrated in this deliverable will enable validating DECICE APIs that will provide features related to this objective.
(O4) Design and implement a Dynamic Digital Twin of the system with AI-based prediction capabilities as an integral part of the solution.	The described infrastructure will enable partners to implement the Digital Twin.
(O5) Demonstrate the usability and benefits of the DECICE solution for real-life use cases.	The current version of the infrastructure and the software stack is the foundation of the DECICE final working infrastructure. Its evolution and refinement will enable the support and analysis of all the use cases.
(O6) Design a solution that enables service deployment with a high level of trustworthiness and compliance with relevant security frameworks.	The architecture described in this deliverable does not yet cover these aspects; they will be added on top during the rest of the project and following iterations.

4 Changes Made and/or Difficulties Encountered

The original plan for the DECICE project outlined a three-phase deployment strategy. The first phase, termed *Preliminary Deployment* aimed to establish an infrastructure according to the specifications detailed in Task 5.2, as summarized in the "Development Environment Specification" (D5.2). This phase was intended to be executed at a single site. The second phase, *Testing*, planned to expand this setup to include a second site, thereby enhancing the complexity and reach of the testing environment. Phase 3 is about the full deployment of the hardware and software infrastructure and will be handled in an upcoming Deliverable.

Challenges Encountered:

- **Procurement delays:** the procurement of essential physical infrastructure, managed by E4, has experienced significant delays. These delays stem from ongoing global supply chain issues affecting the availability of necessary hardware components. As a result, the start of the infrastructure deployment has been postponed, impacting the overall project timeline.
- **Deployment delays:** due to the aforementioned procurement challenges, the availability of the DECICE final infrastructure for both Phase 1 and Phase 2 is now expected to be delayed by several months.

To mitigate these problems, the following actions have been taken:

- E4 deployed a computing cluster consisting of legacy components to offer CPUs, GPUs, and edge computing resources, which will be used until the final DECICE infrastructure is up and running.
- E4 worked closely with the partners responsible for UC1 and UC3 to complete a working deployment. Specifically, Phase 1 is complete regarding the deployment of UC1 and UC3 on the local cluster, while the porting of Phase 2, which requires deployment on a distributed K8s cluster, is still in progress.
- In order to provide a complete overview of the first results with existing use cases, the implementation of UC2 was postponed, instead focusing efforts on UC1 and UC3. The characteristics of UC2 did not, in fact, make it possible to move the data outside the infrastructure on which it was collected for security and privacy reasons (at the time of finalizing this deliverable).

To meet the deadline for D5.4, the revised plan, considering the delays associated with some of the actions outlined in the contingency plan above, is structured around the following steps:

1. Full deployment of UC2.
2. Demonstration of UC1 considering a distributed cluster, to be agreed between E4 and MarUn (according to Phase 2).
3. Implementation of Phase 3 for all the use cases: the results will be summarized in D5.4.

5 Sustainability

This deliverable is closely related to other Work Packages. In particular, we engaged partners from WP2, WP3, and WP4 in the discussion to better align with the requirements of the use cases and establish the necessary links to interact with the middleware and tools developed during the project.

An important lesson learned was the need to gradually integrate the features of the use cases into the deployment architecture. We started from an initial baseline architecture to have better control over possible integration issues before committing to the final DECICE framework. To facilitate this process, joint and focused technical video calls were scheduled twice a week with the use case providers during the last two months before the release of the deliverable.

6 Dissemination, Engagement and Uptake of Results

6.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Description of the project, the audience for this deliverable is the **general public (PU)** as listed in the Table below.

6.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

The current activities have not been included in any dissemination event as of now.

A post on the official website and social media channels was published to give visibility to this specific stage of the project.

✓	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This report is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

MarUn and BigTRI are currently working on a research paper about UC1 and its relation to the DECICE concept.

6.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

None.

7 Detailed Report on the Deliverable

In this deliverable, starting from a recap of the specifications of the Use Cases provided in D5.1 and of the infrastructure provided in D5.2, we are describing how the Use Cases are mapped on the baseline architecture. We start by providing information about the deployment of prototype Use Cases; then, we describe the validation process and the performance evaluation.

7.1 Development Environment specification: a recap of the previous steps

In the ongoing evolution of the DECICE project, Deliverables D5.1 and D5.2 represented two key steps, outlining the needs expressed by the use case owners and the decisions taken by the Working Group about the infrastructure deployment. This section connects the foundational insights from Deliverable D5.1 and the strategic decisions outlined in Deliverable D5.2 with the upcoming actions in D5.3.

7.1.1 Summary of use case needs and key requirements

Deliverable D5.1 detailed the technical requirements and challenges for the three use cases in the DECICE project, each with specific performance and functional requirements essential for validating the success and real-world applicability of the DECICE framework.

UC1 - Intelligent Intersection with VRU Detection

This use case, owned by Marmara University, focuses on enhancing safety and efficiency in urban traffic through real-time processing capabilities at intersections. It requires robust edge computing solutions to manage data from multiple sensors and ensure timely decision-making.

Key components to be deployed in the Core Project Infrastructure ¹:

¹This bullet points list includes the components to be deployed in the core infrastructure activated for the Project. Particularly, it is related to the infrastructure directly managed and made available by E4.

- *IoT Device(s)*: cameras and RSUs. In the test infrastructure, they will be emulated using VMs;
- *Edge device(s)*: aimed at running object detection model and inference/training. Edge device requires GPU power for inference;
- *Virtual Machines*: to maintain applications' services and databases and to train and improve the base object recognition model.

Key functional requirements to be validated in the architecture deployment:

- *Latency*: The response time from data capture to action must be minimal to ensure real-time processing for immediate traffic decisions. End-to-end latency should be around 20 ms (milliseconds) in ideal conditions. For the processing of a single frame captured from the intersection, the delay caused by transferring a single frame to the edge device + the delay caused by processing a single frame + delay caused by transferring the output of the inference must be ≤ 300 ms.
- *Storage*: Sufficient storage should be present for recording captured video frames. Also, the edge devices should have enough storage to store the models for object detection and localization.
- *Bandwidth*: At least 1Gbps bandwidth is required for the network to connect the camera to the edge device and the edge device to the Road Side Unit.
- *Reliability*: The system must maintain high availability with a target reliability rate of 99%.
- *Data Integrity*: Securely handling and transmitting data is required to prevent loss and corruption, which is critical for maintaining system trust and effectiveness.

UC2 - Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) scans

MRI (Magnetic Resonance Imaging) scans generate high-resolution images requiring significant computing power and data handling capabilities. This use case, owned by GWDG, is particularly sensitive due to the personal nature of the medical data involved.

Key components to be deployed in the Core Project Infrastructure ²:

- *Cloud and/or HPC system*: to store images and compute them.

Key functional requirements to be validated in the architecture deployment:

- *Data Security*: Ensuring patient data is securely stored and transmitted, complying with health data regulations such as GDPR.
- *Storage Scalability*: The architecture must scale to accommodate growing data sizes as imaging technology advances.

²Due to highly confidential dementia patient data and GDPR compliance, real data of this use case cannot be moved outside the GWDG cluster yet. A proper interaction with E4-managed infrastructure will be defined.

- *Computation time*: The computation must be completed within a strict time limit and should not exceed 10 minutes. Meeting this deadline is strictly connected to the computational power of the system.
- *Reliability*: Clinics and radiologists cannot afford to wait for a system that is only occasionally available. In any case, a target reliability is not explicitly specified.

UC3 - Disaster management and emergency response

This use case, owned by the University of Bologna, aims to create a digital platform that utilizes data from drones and satellites to support emergency operations, requiring real-time data processing and high adaptability to dynamic conditions.

Key components to be deployed in the Core Project Infrastructure:

- *Edge systems (Base Station and Autonomous Robots)*: to “simulate” in the cloud the management and the orchestration of operations related to the autonomous robotic agents (drones).
- *Cloud and/or HPC systems*: aimed at performing computationally intensive tasks more precisely than those performed on edge systems.

Key functional requirements to be validated in the architecture deployment:

- *Cloud Storage*: 100 GB - 1 TB
- *Latency*: This will be monitored to match the working conditions of the use case. No target value is defined a priori.
- *Data Security*: it is mandatory to avoid storing data on insecure devices.
- *BS (Base Station)*: Multi-core, x8086, +2GHz CPU, +8GB RAM.
- *AR (Autonomous Robots)*: Multi-core, ARM, 1-2GHz CPU, 1-4 GB RAM in case of optimal solution. Up to +8GB if the solution is not optimized.

7.1.2 Recap of main decisions concerning the architecture and provisioning strategies

Deliverable D5.2: “Development Environment Specification” outlined the architecture setup, focusing heavily on selecting hardware that would support the diverse needs of the DECICE framework.

Architecture Overview

The architecture laid out in D5.2 provides a robust foundation for deploying the DECICE framework, incorporating advanced technologies and hardware solutions designed to ensure flexibility, scalability, and performance. Deployment infrastructure is mainly in charge of E4 Partner (Work Package 5 leader). Nevertheless, additional resources can be used for the deployment:

- Huawei AI and Computing at Goethe University (HAICGU) is a cluster based on Huawei HPC solutions. This cluster is installed at the Goethe University of Frankfurt and is maintained by the Open Edge and HPC initiative (OEHI). The Goethe University Frankfurt is part of the National High-Performance Computing Alliance.

- GWDG computational resources.
- Specific resources that are directly owned and made available by each use case owner.

Hardware Configuration

The hardware choices are central to the architecture's ability to meet the high demands of the DECICE project's use cases. Key components of the hardware configuration include:

- *Master and Worker Nodes*: High-performance servers are deployed as master and worker nodes to manage and execute tasks within the DECICE environment. These servers have powerful CPUs and sufficient memory to efficiently handle large datasets and complex computations.
- *GPU Nodes*: Given the intensive computing requirements, especially for use cases like MRI scans (UC2) and VRU Safety (UC1), GPU nodes are integrated to provide additional processing power. These nodes are outfitted with high-end GPUs capable of performing parallel processing tasks that accelerate machine learning models and real-time data analysis.
- *IoT and Edge Devices*: To address the real-time processing needs at the edge, especially in smart city infrastructure and disaster management scenarios. These devices are selected based on their ability to operate in diverse environmental conditions and compatibility with low-latency communication technologies.
- *Storage Solutions*: Scalable storage systems are implemented to manage the vast amounts of data generated, especially from MRI scans and sensor data in smart city applications. These storage solutions ensure data redundancy, high availability, and quick access to improve the system's overall efficiency.
- *Network Equipment*: Efficient networking hardware supports the high-bandwidth and low-latency requirements for seamless data transfer across the cloud, edge, and end devices. Routers, switches, and other networking devices ensure reliable and secure communications.

Figure 1: DECICE development environment.

Provisioning and Node Management

Foreman was chosen as the key tool for bare metal provisioning and node management within the DECICE infrastructure. It facilitates the automated deployment of operating systems on new hardware and supports the provisioning of both physical and virtual environments. This tool ensures that systems are consistently configured according to defined policies, which is crucial for maintaining reproducibility and minimizing manual intervention across the project's life cycle.

Continuous Integration/Continuous Delivery (CI/CD)

The CI/CD toolchain is managed via Jenkins and GitLab. Jenkins provides a highly customizable environment with a vast ecosystem of plugins, supporting a wide range of functionalities to enhance versatility and adaptability. GitLab complements this by hosting the repositories, managing code reviews, issue tracking, and automating the deployment pipelines within the same environment. This integration allows for real-time testing and reporting on isolated changes, facilitating rapid detection of defects and seamless code integration across project components.

Virtualization

OpenStack was selected as the virtualization platform, offering extensive infrastructure management capabilities. This platform supports comprehensive API-driven management of cloud resources, which is essential for a scalable and flexible cloud environment. OpenStack's modular architecture allows DECICE to customize the deployment according to project-specific needs, including managing VM instances, security groups, and network configurations from a unified web-based interface.

Containerization

Kubernetes (K8s) was adopted for container orchestration, automating containerized applications' deployment, scaling, and management [k8]. This choice supports DECICE's need for a robust system capable of managing microservices-based applications across cloud and edge environments. Container orchestration will be extended to the edge devices via KubeEdge. KubeEdge integrates with K8s to extend workloads to the edge.

7.2 Baseline architecture

This section contains details of the hardware and software used for D5.3 as a "workaround" (due to the aforementioned delays in procuring the final hardware).

Specifically, a **baseline architecture** was identified and activated, as shown in Figure 2. This architecture must be considered the starting point for mapping use cases and validating the deployment process.

In the final part of the section, the plan for the transition from the current system to the final architecture will be provided as soon as the hardware is available and the procurement and installation process is complete.

In terms of accessibility, the baseline infrastructure can be reached via SSH (Secure Shell Protocol) through the VPN service provided by E4), using the credentials username, password.

Once logged in, the user can:

- Access the cluster, which consists of a node that can act as both a master node and a worker node.
- Access other machines to deploy applications outside the cluster (for example, in the form of external stimuli - external data generators).

Please note that accessing these machines also requires SSH authentication username and password. Once applications are deployed within the cluster, the user can monitor the overall health using the `kubect1` CLI command.

Figure 2: The Baseline Architecture.

7.3 Mapping use cases on the baseline architecture

This section explores UC1, UC2, and UC3, and for each of them, it illustrates the requirements (hardware and software) and shows how they have been mapped on the baseline architecture described above. For what concerns UC2, it has been mapped on GWDG GPU cluster. For both use cases, E4 followed an incremental approach involving the project partners (UC owners). An initial version has been kickstarted for each use case, gradually adding features until a deployable version of the use case is achieved.

7.3.1 UC1

Use Case 1 focuses on increasing safety for Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs), particularly in intersections, using mounted cameras that are being used for 3D position sensing of road users (including VRUs) and V2X communications for informing other intersection users (connected vehicles) about the positions of VRUS. The use case consists of basically 3 elements for a single intersection: mounted monocular camera(s), computing nodes (potentially edge nodes, while cloud nodes are also applicable as long as the timing restrictions are fulfilled), and roadside units (RSUs). In the described setup, the frames captured by the camera(s) are continuously fed to the computing node(s),

and outputs produced by monocular 3D positioning models are fed to the RSUs to be broadcasted as Collective Perception Messages (CPMs) to the connected vehicles in the vicinity.

Figure 3: Example camera view and illustration of Use Case 1 VRU Safety Application

VRU Safety Application is subjected to various requirements on the end-to-end delay, network delay, network reliability, and inference performance by standards such as 3GPP TS 22.186 R17 and ETSI TS 103 302 (requirements have been detailed in D5.1). To demonstrate scheduling and other capabilities of DECICE (validating that restrictions by standards are fulfilled and that baseline is improved), a multi-intersection environment has been chosen to produce scenarios in this use case. This demonstration activity aims to emulate the UC testbed (MarUn C-ITS testing infrastructure) on the baseline architecture. To do this, the camera is represented by an executable (multi)casting pre-recorded video frames, and the RSU mimics the real RSU by only containing the receiving interfaces.

Figure 4 shows the Use Case 1 deployment, which consists of a virtual machine placed outside the Kubernetes clusters that stimulates the deployed pods with the frames of a sample video. The pods consist of Python applications that perform inference on the provided frames. The applications are deployed on the GPU node, leveraging the CUDA capabilities. Compute Unified Device Architecture (CUDA) is a proprietary NVIDIA parallel computing platform and application programming interface (API) that allows the software to use certain types of graphics processing units (GPUs) for accelerated general-purpose processing.

7.3.2 UC2

Use Case 2 focuses on improving the efficiency and accuracy of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) scans by integrating advanced processing techniques. In future applications, doctors receive decision support via generated quantitative analysis of MR images. This process is time critical since the analysis must be provided to the doctor along with the images within minutes. DECICE will provide an efficient, fast processing, low latency, energy-efficient edge and cloud computing continuum that also considers the load at edge nodes due to the spatiotemporal variation of the users.

The use case consists of several critical components: high-resolution MRI scanners, computing nodes (both edge and cloud-based), and specialized imaging software. Even though a first run through

Figure 4: Mapping of UC1 on the baseline architecture.

of the processing pipeline could not be setup on the E4 legacy cluster due to GDPR compliancy, a generic pipeline has been built which can easily be modified and deployed on any hardware cluster that meets the computational requirements. Once synthetic MRI data has been created or the currently used data has been anonymized, deploying the processing pipeline on our DECICE cluster will become fairly moderate task to achieve. To keep up with the benchmark of providing reliable processing results within a 10 minute time frame, it is crucial to provide a sophisticated hardware cluster. First tests on our GWDG GPU cluster show that even though building the container for a deployment on an HPC system takes longer than expected (around 20 minutes), the actual computing time is just over 5 minutes which is a promising first result for the future DECICE platform with a lot of leeway to perform additional screenings or run throughs.

To achieve this endeavor we first prepared a container for our HPC system by pulling the base image from the docker registry and converting it into a singularity container. The library we used is *fastsurfer*³. We mounted the data and the license required by the library to the container and deployed it via Slurm. The computation took place on a NVIDIA RTX 5000 GPU and delivered results in 5 minutes. Future steps will include incorporating edge devices to test computation time on smaller devices, scaling up the image processing (a first dataset was around 60MB in size but other datasets can be up to 250mb large) and network metrics to account for the possibility that edge devices might not finish computation within 10 minutes and the data needs to send to a cloud service. Figure 5 shows a schematic run for MRI images processing on the heterogeneous DECICE cluster.

7.3.3 UC3

Use Case 3 (UC3) focuses on developing an open digital platform that enhances the data available to emergency response teams involved in search-and-rescue operations. The information is collected from the field with autonomous drones, specifically quadrotors, and sent to a ground station and a

³<https://deep-mi.org/research/fast-surfer/>

Figure 5: MRI Scan

cloud infrastructure. This will allow the operator to control the data flow between the computing devices and provide adaptability to the emergency scenario, such as the size of the area to be explored, recognition tasks to be performed, and energy availability.

Figure 6: Illustration of UC3 Application

In UC3, ROS2 has been used as a platform to implement the necessary software stack and configuration for managing communication and execution of tasks across robots and other computing nodes.

Robot Operating System 2 ROS2 (Robot Operating System 2) is a flexible framework for writing robot software. It provides a collection of tools, libraries, and conventions to simplify the task of creating complex and robust robot behavior across a wide variety of robotic platforms. ROS2

supports distributed computing and real-time performance and is designed to work seamlessly with modern middleware technologies, making it suitable for both research and industrial applications.

Since the term "node" is common in both K8s and ROS2, it can be useful to provide a brief explanation of the differences between ROS2 nodes and Kubernetes nodes below to prevent any confusion.

In ROS2, a node is a fundamental unit of computation that performs specific tasks, such as processing sensor data or controlling actuators. Each ROS2 node operates independently and can communicate with other nodes through topics, services, and actions, facilitating modular and scalable robot software development.

In Kubernetes (K8s), a node is a physical or virtual machine that runs containerized applications. A Kubernetes node includes the necessary services to run pods, which are the smallest deployable units in K8s, typically running one or more containers. While ROS2 nodes focus on robotic functionalities, K8s nodes focus on orchestrating and managing containerized workloads, providing a scalable and resilient infrastructure for applications.

For UC3, different ROS2 nodes were created to control drones and process data from the field. These ROS2 nodes are deployed as Kubernetes pods. Additionally, an environmental simulator was deployed as a virtual machine (VM). This VM is integrated into the K8s cluster to leverage the K8s CNI (Container Network Interface) and networking features.

To prevent the K8s scheduler from assigning any pods to the environmental simulation VM (node), a specific **taint** was used. In Kubernetes, taints and tolerations are used to control the scheduling of pods onto nodes in a cluster. They help to ensure that only certain pods are placed on specific nodes, based on specific conditions and requirements.

UNIBO adapted UC3 for the K8s ecosystem, not being designed natively for this architecture. After testing the deployment on the local cluster, UNIBO deployed it on the E4 cluster. Figure 8 shows a successful communication test between the "Talker" and "Listener" ROS2 pods, demonstrating the robustness of the Kubernetes networking and its suitability for complex, distributed robotics applications. The logs from the "Listener" pod confirmed the receipt of sequential "Hello World" messages from the "Talker" pod, indicating effective inter-pod communication over the Kubernetes-managed network. This result not only validates the Kubernetes configuration for ROS2 applications but also underscores the platform's capability to maintain consistent and reliable communication channels across distributed components. Such evidence supports Kubernetes as a viable solution for deploying scalable, network-intensive robotics applications, providing a strong foundation for further exploration and development in cloud robotics.

```
Every 2.0s: kubectll get pods -A -o wide
```

NAMESPACE	NAME	READY	STATUS	RESTARTS	AGE	IP	NODE	NOMINATED NODE	READINESS GATES
default	ros-699d64449f-29hxf	1/1	Running	0	2m13s	10.44.0.2	icnode85.e4red	<none>	<none>
default	ros-699d64449f-1q2n	1/1	Running	0	2m12s	18.32.0.4	redmaster.e4red	<none>	<none>
default	ros-699d64449f-rtk22	1/1	Running	0	2m13s	10.44.0.1	icnode85.e4red	<none>	<none>
kube-system	coredns-7db68ff4d-2msrb	1/1	Running	0	90m	18.32.0.3	redmaster.e4red	<none>	<none>
kube-system	coredns-7db68ff4d-lqjqt	1/1	Running	0	90m	18.32.0.2	redmaster.e4red	<none>	<none>
kube-system	etcd-redmaster.e4red	1/1	Running	14	91m	172.18.16.61	redmaster.e4red	<none>	<none>
kube-system	kube-apiserver-redmaster.e4red	1/1	Running	14	91m	172.18.16.61	redmaster.e4red	<none>	<none>
kube-system	kube-controller-manager-redmaster.e4red	1/1	Running	14	91m	172.18.16.61	redmaster.e4red	<none>	<none>
kube-system	kube-proxy-swrm	1/1	Running	0	90m	172.18.17.210	icnode85.e4red	<none>	<none>
kube-system	kube-proxy-95ngb	1/1	Running	0	90m	172.18.16.61	redmaster.e4red	<none>	<none>
kube-system	kube-proxy-3tp49	1/1	Running	0	41m	10.0.2.15	humblest1t	<none>	<none>
kube-system	kube-scheduler-redmaster.e4red	1/1	Running	14	91m	172.18.16.61	redmaster.e4red	<none>	<none>
kube-system	weave-net-t6qvn	2/2	Running	0	76m	172.18.17.210	icnode85.e4red	<none>	<none>
kube-system	weave-net-wkltv	2/2	Running	0	90m	172.18.16.61	redmaster.e4red	<none>	<none>
kube-system	weave-net-zd75p	2/2	Running	0	41m	10.0.2.15	humblest1t	<none>	<none>

Figure 7: Kubernetes Resources at E4 K8s.

- Roadside Unit (RSU, CPU node): Mimicking the RSU in the real environment by receiving coordinates detected by the inference
- Inference (GPU Node): Processes video frames and provides coordinates to the RSU

The communication of the pods on different machines was tested; in particular, it has been checked that:

- the camera emulator pod continuously generates video stimuli
- the inference application pod receives and processes them

Figure 12: Control panel to monitor the UC1 use of resources created with Grafana.

Figure 13: Example of the Grafana visual interface to visualize the structure of UC1.

Figure 14: A view of the use of resources of a UC1 worker node.

Figure 15 shows the data transfer from the camera emulator to RSU. The purple line shows the network traffic on the interface of the camera emulator pod. Frames are sent with a rate around 2Mb/s.

Figure 15: Network traffic observed between the camera emulator and the inference.

The latency between nodes and devices is an essential metric for UC1. Figure 16 shows the latency between:

- Camera emulator and inference (Purple Line)
- RSU and inference (Red Line)
- Camera and RSU (Yellow Line)

These metrics will provide information for the scheduler in order to satisfy the performance requirements while deploying the workloads of VRU safety application.

Figure 16: Latency between the components of UC1.

The delay caused by the inference is another important metric while scheduling UC1 workloads. It is shown in Figure 17, while the inference is running on the GPU node. Processing by inference puts a delay of approximately 13ms. Only one inference pod is being run on the GPU node.

GPU Metrics on the Icnode05.e4red (GPU Node) are shown in the Figure 18, representing the effects of running inference application. A single inference pod is deployed on the GPU Node.

Figure 17: The delay caused by the inference.

Figure 18: GPU Metrics while the inference is running.

7.4.2 UC2

To perform calculations in Use Case 2, raw, anonymized MRI data was obtained, with a dataset size of 590 MB. A Singularity container was prepared by pulling the FastSurfer Docker image and converting it into a Singularity Image File (SIF) format. Command line options were configured according to examples provided on the FastSurfer⁴ website. A Slurm batch file was prepared to run this container and input data on an HPC system, and the job was subsequently submitted.

Jobs were executed on different GPU configurations, such as NVIDIA RTX5000 and V100 GPUs. The most recent job, run on an NVIDIA V100, consumed an average of 4300MB of memory. Figure 19 illustrates the GPU usage of a job during a certain time interval.

The average running time for these various Slurm jobs was around 8 minutes. The command line options used during computation were standard examples from the FastSurfer website, with no optimization performed to reduce job running times. By applying optimization methods and using more suitable command line options, the performance of the pipeline can be significantly improved.

Future improvements will focus on optimizing these command line options and exploring various performance enhancement methods. Such optimizations are expected to reduce running times and

⁴<https://deep-mi.org/FastSurfer/dev/overview/EXAMPLES.html#example-2-fastsurfer-singularity>

```

Every 2,0s: nvidia-smi
Wed May 29 10:24:08 2024
+-----+
| NVIDIA-SMI 530.30.02                Driver Version: 530.30.02   CUDA Version: 12.1   |
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
| GPU  Name                               Persistence-M| Bus-Id        Disp.A | Volatile Uncorr. ECC |
| Fan  Temp  Perf              Pwr:Usage/Cap|      Memory-Usage | GPU-Util  Compute M. |
|=====+=====+=====+=====+=====+=====+
|  0   Tesla V100-PCIE-32GB                On          | 00000000:88:00:0  Off  |      0          | |
| N/A   42C    P0              126W / 250W| 4226MiB / 32768MiB |      58%    Default |
|                                           |                      |                      | N/A          |
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
+-----+
| Processes:
| GPU  GI  CI           PID  Type  Process name          GPU Memory
|   ID  ID  ID                   |    |             | Usage
|-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
|  0   N/A N/A         22405   C   python3.10           4222MiB
|-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+

```

Figure 19: GPU resource usage for UC2 Slurm jobs

improve overall pipeline efficiency, leveraging the full potential of the hardware and software used.

7.4.3 UC3

In this phase of the study, we conducted validation tests on ROS2 node communication between ROS2 pods. We also validated the availability of metrics in the monitoring system and assessed the capabilities of the Kubernetes (K8s) cluster and monitoring software stack. Figure 20 displays the node-level metrics, including CPU usage, memory usage, disk I/O and space usage, and network traffic received and sent by different network interfaces.

Figure 20: UC3 Grafana dashboard.

7.5 Next steps

To effectively transition from the current status of the deployment through Phase 3 and into Task T5.4 (Performance evaluation), a structured plan must be developed that aligns with the project goals and accounts for any challenges encountered in the earlier phases. Here's an outlined plan for moving forward into the next stages:

7.5.1 Full deployment

Objective: To test the DECICE project development environment in its final configuration, using provisioned hardware plus geographically and functionally distributed resources, including infrastructures provided by other partners.

Timing and roles:

- Timing: Begin after successful completion of Phases 1 and 2.
- Roles: E4, HWDU, GWDG, BIGTRI, MARUN, and TOP-IX collaboratively deploy the infrastructure. TOP-IX will focus on setting up networks for geographically distributed architectures. E4 will take care of the final infrastructure. Other partners will integrate their respective systems and technologies into the unified project environment.

Key activities:

- Extensive validation of Phase 2 (regional scale deployment) for UC1 and UC3.
- Perform UC2 deployment accordingly to UC1 and UC3. A critical aspect to be further analyzed is the distribution of data submitted to GDPR restrictions
- Transfer the environment from baseline architecture to final architecture when the procurement of new hardware will be completed.
- Integrate public clouds and partner infrastructures to ensure seamless operation across different geographic locations.
- Ensure all systems are interoperable and meet the project's technical and security requirements.
- Provide all project partners with access to the project development environment, ensuring they have the necessary permissions and resources to conduct tests and evaluations.
- Conduct initial system tests to ensure stability and operational readiness.
- Address any issues identified during these tests before moving to comprehensive performance evaluations.

7.5.2 Task T5.4: Performance evaluation

Objective: To conduct an in-depth operational evaluation of the DECICE framework performances, focusing on specified use cases and collecting key performance metrics.

Timing and roles:

- Timing: Starting after D5.3 submission to the end of the project.

- Roles: BIGTRI and MARUN will focus on collecting performance metrics for the use cases led by MARUN. GWDG and UNIBO will collect data for their respective use cases. E4 and TOP-IX will evaluate the broader DECICE framework, with TOP-IX focusing on network parameters.

Key activities:

- Implement testing scenarios covering regular and uncommon system states to identify performance bottlenecks and operational efficiencies.
- Include stress tests and scenarios to assess system robustness and resilience.
- Analyze collected data to assess the performance and effectiveness of the DECICE framework.
- Identify areas for improvement and potential updates to enhance system performance and user experience.
- Compile findings into detailed reports for review by project stakeholders.
- Use insights from these evaluations to refine and optimize the DECICE framework and its components continuously.
- Gather feedback from all partners and stakeholders to incorporate their insights and priorities into the continuous development cycle.

This structured approach will help maintain alignment with project objectives and ensure the framework's suitability for real-world applications.

8 References

[k8] *Kubernetes*. <https://kubernetes.io>. Accessed: 24-05-2024.